

CODEN [USA] : IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**FREQUENCY OF DEPRESSION IN DOCTORS WORKING IN
VARIOUS DEPARTMENT S OF A FEDERAL GOVERNMENT
HOSPITAL OF LAHORE**¹Syeda Aiman Zahra Naqvi, ²Hina Ghufraan, ³Saim Shahid¹Services Hospital Lahore²Govt general Hospital Ghulam Muhammad Abad Faisalabad³RHC Satiana, Faisalabad**Article Received:** June 2020**Accepted:** July 2020**Published:** August 2020**Abstract:**

Doctors in every hospital play an important role. After doctors they take care of patients so their care should also be needed. If they will be physically fit and will not suffering from any type of stress or feeling any insecurity, they can take care of patients in excellent way. So to check problems Doctors are facing as depression who are working in different hospital of Lahore, we do this study. We ask multiple questions to Doctors who was in the age of about 26-39 of age. We take survey from different number of Doctors as approximately 240 Doctors who was working in different departments of hospitals as some of them was performing their duties in I.C.U, children wards, reception area, psychological departments and many other departments of hospital. We use different type of questions to check the level of issues they are facing and collect most appropriate data. Response from Doctors which we get in form of survey was about 93%. By specific testing method we take results from answers of our survey. So the results which we get showed that total assessment of depression in nursing was about 93%. About 38% of them were suffering with moderate level of depression and 15% suffer from stern depression. We have also examined that the rate of depression was increased in those nursing who was working where conditions become serious as in I.C.U, operation theaters etc. It is concluded that increasing level of depression and stress in nursing make them mentally disturbed.

Keywords: Doctors conditions, I.C.U, mental stress, depression.**Corresponding author:****Syeda Aiman Zahra Naqvi,**

Services Hospital Lahore

QR code

Please cite this article in press Syeda Aiman Zahra Naqvi et al, *Frequency Of Depression In Doctors Working In Various Department S Of A Federal Government Hospital Of Lahore., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(08)*

INTRODUCTION:

If we discuss about depression, mainly it occurs which some serious reasons as if we work in conditions which are disturbing our mind [1]. If we will not relax mentally then we cannot perform any task with proper attention and care [2]. It not only in Pakistan but whole world is affected with it and it causes severe issues. If we check results about either ratio of women is increased in men or in women, so results we find was that as level of depression is increased in women than men [3]. So if we want to check why ratio of depression is increased in women than we can see that hormones changing occur in women which move them toward depression [4]. About 6-13% males will be depressed but in women ratio will be 20-25% [5]. If we discussed about the percentage of depression in men and women it is as in women it is 4-8% and in men it is 2-3%. Some how cause of suicide is due to depression [6]. Doctors who are performing their duties in different departments play important role in value of hospital and to take care of patients [7]. About 85% are female Doctors who are working in different hospitals. Depression occur in Doctors increased due they work with patients who suffer from different diseases and feel pain every time [8]. So their mental issues should be resolved because when they will be depressed they will transfer negative vibes toward their patients and they cannot pay proper attention on their duty and toward their patients [9].

METHODOLOGY:

We took a study-based survey in which we ask different question to Doctors who work in Jinnah hospital, Lahore. There were a lot of patients in this hospital and number of Doctors was performing their duties in this hospital. We ask different number of questions to them to check the main cause of depression in Doctors. We collect data from Doctors who were in the age of 26-36 years. These Doctors were working there years ago. We handover a survey page where we write different type of question to check their level of depression either they are comfortable with their job or facing some hardships or mental stress during their duties or even after their duty timings. We take this survey from those Doctors who spend most of their time with patients. After getting their answers, we started making results. We consult with psychiatrics also and make result as Doctors who are doing their duties with patients. We concluded it that proper check and balance of their duty timing. They should take rest must. In this way when they will take proper sleep it will help them to get healthy mind without stress or if we see that someone is new on job and suffering this type of issue as mental stress which causes depression we have to treat her with positive things by telling her positive sides of her job and make able to perform

duty very well in this way by taking care of Doctors we make them able to get rid of this type of issue as depression. On the other hand it is very most to make them physically fit, proper training of Doctors and they should do physical exercises and mental exercises as yoga to relax themselves and perform their duties in a very good so when they will not be stress and will relax mentally they will do proper care of their patients and their patients will be happy with their work. So atmosphere of hospital will be good.

RESULTS:

We take this survey from Doctors who were working with different department and were in the age of about 26-39 years. About 60% was graduated Doctors. Some of them were educated as master level. We take survey in form of question answer session and believed that Doctors who were working with most serious patients as in emergency, they show severe type of depression symptoms as compared to other Doctors. So their level of depression also connects with their work, in which department either they are performing their duties, it affect their mental activities a lot. We receive different number of ratios while taking survey but over all we receive approx 93% results that show positive results toward depression. So it is estimated that most of Doctors are depressed due to atmosphere present around them.

Prevalence of Depression

Fig No. 01

Table: 1 Association of Depression with deployment at different departments

Variables		Classification of Depression				Chi-Square value	p-value
		Normal (1-13)	Mild Depression (14-26)	Moderate Depression (27-39)	Severe Depression (40-52)		
Department	Medicine	4(1.7%)	28(12%)	13(5.5%)	1(0.4%)	40.608	0.000
	Surgery	6(2.5%)	13(5.5%)	18(7.7%)	7(3%)		
	Paedes	8(3.4%)	17(7.3%)	18(7.7%)	4(1.7%)		
	MCH	1(0.4%)	19(8.1%)	16(6.8%)	11(4.7%)		
	Other	0(0%)	10(4.3%)	30(12%)	9(3.8%)		

DISCUSSION:

We make a study report to find the level of depression in Doctors working in hospital [10]. We mainly check out and take survey from those Doctors who are performing their duties most of time with their patients. We take this survey from about 240 respondents [11]. After doing that survey and getting answers from Doctors, we collect whole data, find results. After finding results we prepare it as a report study [12]. It shows that about 93% Doctors was suffering from depression but if we see normal women who are taking care of their families and children or doing job, their ratio is 34% [13]. Level of depression in Doctors in different countries is also present in increased rate as compared to other population [14]. It may be due to multiple stresses they are facing as may be they are facing stress from home members, or low level of income or if they are working in the department where people face serious injuries. We find three different level of depression in Doctors as about 38% Doctors was suffering from normal depression, 42% was having middle level depression but 15% was those who show severe symptoms of depression [15]. So we have seen that Doctors who are working in serious conditions show more depression level as compare to those Doctors who are working in other departments of hospitals. Atmosphere affects a lot and serious conditions of patients and emergency wards conditions make them mentally depressed and stressed. So to avoid all this they should have proper knowledge about it and do exercises which make them mentally and physically fit [16].

CONCLUSION:

With this report, we have concluded that Doctors working in hospitals mainly those who spend most of their time with patients and working in emergency departments, in intensive care units or where people suffer from severe diseases. It increase the level of stress in Doctors and make them mentally disturb. Then feel down and are not able to do their tasks with more energy and give proper care to their patients.

REFERENCES:

1. Lu, L., Dong, M., Wang, S. B., Zhang, L., Ng, C. H., Ungvari, G. S., ... & Xiang, Y. T. (2020). Prevalence of workplace violence against health-care professionals in China: a comprehensive meta-analysis of observational surveys. *Trauma, Violence, & Abuse*, 21(3), 498-509.
2. Li, Y. L., Li, R. Q., Qiu, D., & Xiao, S. Y. (2020). Prevalence of workplace physical violence against health care professionals by patients and visitors: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *International journal of*

environmental research and public health, 17(1), 299.

3. Hossain, M. M., Sharma, R., Tasnim, S., Al Kibria, G. M., Sultana, A., & Saxena, T. (2020). Prevalence, Characteristics, and Associated Factors of Workplace Violence Against Healthcare Professionals in India: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis. *medRxiv*.
4. Ali, M. A., Ali, N. A., & Alghanem, S. A. (2020). Assessment of anxiety among emergency health care providers and other departments at Bahrain Defense Force Hospital. *Saudi Journal of Emergency Medicine*, 1(2), 63-69.
5. Saeed, H., Siddiqui, S. A., Mansoor, M., & Khan, M. M. (2020). Liaison psychiatry in low & middle income countries: Experiences at the Aga Khan University Hospital (AKUH), Karachi, Pakistan. *Asian journal of psychiatry*, 48, 101889.
6. Salman, M., Mustafa, Z. U., Rao, A. Z., Khan, Q. U. A., Asif, N., Hussain, K., ... & Rashid, A. (2020). Serious Inadequacies in High Alert Medication-Related Knowledge Among Pakistani Doctors: Findings of a Large, Multicenter, Cross-sectional Survey. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*, 11, 1026.
7. Banan, S. H. A. E. (2020). Nurse Managers Practices and Its Relation to Staff Doctors Autonomy and Satisfaction at a Selected Hospital. *International journal of Nursing Didactics*, 10(05), 15-23.
8. Liou, S. R., Liu, H. C., Lin, C. C., Tsai, H. M., & Cheng, C. Y. (2020). An Exploration of Motivation for Disaster Engagement and Its Related Factors among Undergraduate Nursing Students in Taiwan. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(10), 3542.
9. Purwandari, R., Rifai, A., Afandi, A. T., Kurniawan, D. E., & Nur, K. R. M. A Survey of Patients and Doctors Satisfaction toward Patient-Centered Care (PCC) Implementation in Agricultural-Based Hospital Setting of Jember, Indonesia.
10. Smith, C., van Velthoven, M. H., Truong, N. D., Nam, N. H., Anh, V. P., Al-Ahdal, T. M. A., ... & Pakenham-Walsh, N. (2020). How primary healthcare workers obtain information during consultations to aid safe prescribing in low-income and lower middle-income countries: a systematic review. *BMJ Global Health*, 5(4), e002094.
11. Bukhari, G. M. J., Habibullah, S., Abbasi, M. M. J., & Malik, J. S. (2019). Occupational factors associated with depression in Doctors working in a federal government tertiary care hospital in Islamabad. *Journal of Ayub Medical College Abbottabad*, 31(3), 397-401.

12. Lu, L., Dong, M., Wang, S. B., Zhang, L., Ng, C. H., Ungvari, G. S., ... & Xiang, Y. T. (2020). Prevalence of workplace violence against health-care professionals in China: a comprehensive meta-analysis of observational surveys. *Trauma, Violence, & Abuse, 21*(3), 498-509.
13. Jawaid, S. A., & Imran, N. (2019). Proceedings of International Conference on "Prescription for Wellness: Working Across Boundaries" held at Lahore Pakistan (August 2-3, 2019). *Pakistan journal of medical sciences, 35*(6), 1749.
14. Wang, Z., Zaman, S., Rasool, S. F., uz Zaman, Q., & Amin, A. (2020). Exploring the Relationships Between a Toxic Workplace Environment, Workplace Stress, and Project Success with the Moderating Effect of Organizational Support: Empirical Evidence from Pakistan. *Risk Management and Healthcare Policy, 13*, 1055-1067.
15. Shi, L., Li, G., Hao, J., Wang, W., Chen, W., Liu, S., ... & Zhang, L. (2020). Psychological depletion in physicians and Doctors exposed to workplace violence: a cross-sectional study using propensity score analysis. *International Journal of Nursing Studies, 103*, 103493.
16. Lee, C. C., Tseng, H. C., Wu, L. P., & Chuang, Y. H. (2020). Multiple brief training sessions to improve Doctors' knowledge, attitudes, and confidence regarding nursing care of older adults with depression in long-term care facilities. *Research in Nursing & Health, 43*(1), 114-121.